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Revitalization of Agricultural Education for Self-Reliance in Colleges of Education for Enhancing Students' Involvement in Agriculture in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the Revitalization of Agricultural Education for Self-reliance in Colleges of Education for enhancing students' involvement in Agriculture in Benue State, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study, and three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a survey design. The population was 500 respondents. The sample of 365 respondents, which comprised of 65 lecturers and 300 NCE II students, was drawn purposively from the population. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled Revitalization of Agricultural Education for Self-reliance Questionnaire (RAESRQ) was structured by the researchers from the literature review and used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts. The internal consistency reliability

coefficient of the questionnaire was determined using Cronbach alpha (α). The reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained. The data collected were analyzed using means and standard deviation to answer research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study were that revitalization of agricultural education for self-reliance curriculum in colleges of education for enhancing students' involvement is needed. This is vital for encouraging students to have positive attitudes toward agriculture and training-retraining of lecturers for adequate competencies in the implementation of agricultural education activities in colleges of education. Besides, these will enable production for efficient graduates for self-reliance and job empowerment in Benue State and the nation at large.

Keywords: Education for self-reliance, Agricultural education, Colleges of Education, Self-employment, Agricultural education policy

Introduction

Agriculture is the backbone of Nigerian economy regardless of its low productivity. Several efforts have been put in place to improve the situation including the introduction of Agricultural Education for Self-reliance (AESR) policy to guide Nigerian education system to production and other hands-on activities necessary for community development (Agbulu & Oliatan, 2002). The authors further posit that regardless of its contextual, theoretical and practical relevance, agricultural education for self-reliance policy overtime lost its position in the education circles. Agbulu and Ekele (2004) state that majority of the participants perceived the relevance of reconsidering AESR since it helps to inculcate the positive attitude towards agriculture, equip students with skills, a source of self-employment and improve classroom learning for self-reliance. Furthermore, the authors stated that the key part of this challenge is the preparation of citizens empowered with the knowledge, skills, values and attitudes to attain self-reliance. The National Youth Development Policy (2007) therefore seeks to introduce the principle of self-reliance in aspects of the formal, non-formal, and informal educational system in Benue State and the nation at large. It also asserts that the government of Nigeria needed work to ensure the development of an enabling environment and capacity for all sectors and stakeholders to effectively contribute towards the achievement of sustainability of self-reliance policy of education.

The implementation of this policy supports the government of Nigeria's economic vision. Thus, Nigeria envisions sustainable self-reliance policy of education for employment, good governance and human safety within a green society. Quality education is key for the achievement of this vision, despite the impediments. Twalo (2010) posits that impediments of revitalization were also elicited, like lecturers' inadequate knowledge, skills on planning and utilizing experience developed through the Agriculture Education for self-reliance (AESR), shortage of professionals, and inadequate sources for the implementation. Furthermore, the author explains that assessment of stakeholders' favour rethinking AESR and therefore, appropriate strategies should be considered in the process of revitalizing AESR, taking into consideration the obstacles involved. International Labour Organisation - ILO (2010) assert that stakeholder's meetings were organized in several institutions such as the University Agriculture, Makurdi, among others, for exploring their views on the need for revitalization of AESR in the educational sector for enhancing the student involvement in agriculture. This is important, considering that Agriculture is the backbone of the Nigeria economy, accounting for about half of the national income and slightly more than half of

the merchandised exports of agricultural products to Africa and other continents. The importance of agriculture is further emphasized by the fact that more than 80 percent of Nigerians depend on agriculture as a source of food and employment, especially, to the rural dwellers (FAO, 2015). It is estimated that there are 3.5 million households growing crops only, 2.3 million growing crops and keeping livestock and nearly 58 thousand households keeping livestock only (National Bureau of Statistics, 2013). Those who deal with crops play a very important role in supplying food to the nation. It further mentioned that the main food crops grown are maize, rice, cassava, sorghum, sweet potatoes, bananas, pulses and wheat, among others. While the main cash crops grown are coffee, cashew nuts, tea, cotton, tobacco, and sisal.

Despite its importance, agricultural production has not been convincing enough to meet up the demand. For instance, the average national yield of maize, which is regarded as the main food crop, is 0.75 per hectare expected yield when recommended management practices are used (Agricultural Research Institute – ARI, 2006). In the context of the article, several obstacles worsen the situation and these include inadequate access to important services like agricultural extension, low adoption of recommended new innovations by farmers, less engagement (self-employment) in agriculture for self-reliance policy education of youths among others in Nigeria.

According to National Bureau of Statistics (2013), about 35% percent of 44.9 million population of Nigerians are youths, aged from 15 to 35 years, with an increase in population and expansion of educational opportunities, the number of youths seeking for employment has increased. Available data shows that out of 700,000 graduates who completed their primary, secondary and tertiary education to enter the labour force each year, only 40,000 gets employed into the formal sector. With the above report, it is obvious that there is inadequate implementation of agricultural education for self-reliance policy education, particularly in colleges of education. This necessitated this study on the revitalization of agricultural education for self-reliance in colleges of education for enhancing students' involvement in agriculture in Benue State, Nigeria.

Ahmad, Krogh and Gjotterud (2014) explained that during the implementation of agricultural education for self-reliance (AESR) policy, practical and productive activities (on farm or workshops) were included into school curricula as an integral part of learning process. Therefore, the experienced adults (other than schoolteachers) were pedagogically involved in school learning activities and thus, the aim was to integrate theoretical teaching with the acquisition of practical skills. For this reason, educational efforts were aligned in tandem with the national self-reliance policy education plan. Blentyne and Packer (2009) explained that colleges ran farms or workshops to meet educational objectives and contributed to self-reliance policy education and however, school learning was designed and ran in such a way that it linked well with community needs and realities. Furthermore, the authors explained that graduates (youths) will have a positive attitude towards agriculture and will acquire practical skills that will assist them in engagement in community development activities. Moreover, graduates will be able to engage in agricultural production and other productive self-reliance activities in their environment.

Several efforts have been put in place to improve agricultural production and productivity in Nigeria. These include the engagement of graduates, a group of people who have potential to enhance agriculture for self-reliance policy education. The majority of the

remaining group migrates to urban centres in search of white-collar jobs and worsen rural-urban migration that results in social dislocation and increased crime rate in urban centres and cities. This situation has been mostly fueled by the fact that the majority of these people, especially the youths, have a negative attitude toward agriculture, despite it been the backbone of the country's economy and offering them opportunity of employment. Thus, it necessitates researchers to carry out studies on the revitalization of agriculture for self-reliance in Nigeria.

Following political and economic changes in the mid-1980s, the "education for self-reliance" policy education gradually lost its position in education system due to inadequate support from policymakers, in spite of its overriding contextual, theoretical and practical relevance (Ahmad, Krogh & Gjotterud, 2014). The authors explained that this has made school learning detached from community life and led to a number of challenges such as insufficient outcomes of learning in colleges, inadequate students' capacity to transform classroom knowledge into real-life situations and decline in status of interest as well as positive attitude towards agriculture among graduates in the society at large. A remedy study was conducted by Kadenyi and Kariuki (2011) to call for the transformation of the educational system into one that enhances situated learning. They explained that situated learning is learning that enables learners to develop classroom learning experiences that are directly connected to real-world issues, problems and contexts of life relevance. Based on the previous experiences, education for self-reliance seems to be one of the best options to be adopted. In addition, Agbulu and Wever (2011) stated that most of the youths have inadequate capacity to transfer school knowledge into real life situations necessary for self-employment due to the inadequate implementation of self-reliance policy education in the colleges of education. For this reason, the present study was carried out on the revitalization of agricultural education for self-reliance in colleges of education for enhancing students' involvement in agriculture, in Benue State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following are research questions to guide the study.

- i. What is the importance of agricultural education for enhancing students' involvement in agriculture for self-reliance?
- ii. What are the strategies to impart positive attitudes to students toward agricultural education for involvement in agriculture for self-reliance?
- iii. What are the inadequate competencies of lecturers in imparting agricultural education learning activities into students for self-reliance?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated and will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of NCE students and lecturers on the importance of agricultural education for enhancing students' involvement in agriculture for self-reliance.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of NCE students and lecturers on the strategies of imparting positive attitudes into students toward agricultural education for involvement in agriculture for self-reliance.

- iii. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of NCE students and lecturers on the inadequate competencies of lecturers in imparting agricultural education learning activities for self-reliance.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Benue State, Nigeria. The two colleges of education located in Katsina-ala and Oju towns were selected because of a number of agricultural education skilled courses and development projects introduced to students undergoing the programmes in these colleges. The study adopted a survey research design. The population for the study is 500 lecturers and students. The sample of 365 respondents was purposively drawn from the population. The sample of 365 consisted of 65 lecturers and 300 NCE students in the Agricultural Education department. The instrument used for data collection was a researcher-designed questionnaire titled: Revitalization of Agricultural Education for Self-reliance Questionnaire (RAERQ) with 26 items statement, structured on a four-point scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD). The instrument was validated by three experts: two from Department of Agricultural Education University of Agriculture, Makurdi and one from Department of Agricultural Education College of Education Katsin-ala. The split-half technique was used to ascertain the internal consistency of the questionnaire. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient of 0.75 was obtained. The data collected was analyzed using means and standard deviation to answer research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A benchmark of 2.50 was used for decision on the research questions. The null hypothesis would be upheld when the p-value value was greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results of the study are presented according to research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question One

What is the importance of agricultural education for enhancing students' involvement in agriculture for self-reliance?

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of NCE students and lecturers on the importance of agricultural education for enhancing students' involvement in agriculture for self-reliance.

The answer to this research question and the hypothesis testing are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test Analysis of the Responses of NCE 2 Students and Lecturers on Importance of Agricultural Education for Enhancing Students Involvement Self-reliance in Colleges of Education (N=365)

S/N	Item Statement	\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	p-value	Remark	H ₀
1	Agriculture education for self-reliance (AESR) is pre-requisite in developing human resources for global peace, progress and prosperity.	3.41	0.68	3.42	0.69	0.90	Agreed	NS
2	AESR needs to reconsider its curriculum in colleges of education.	3.28	0.91	3.30	0.90	0.91	Agreed	NS
3	AESR gives qualitative education enabling all students to develop their maximum potentials.	3.33	0.86	3.32	0.32	0.97	Agreed	NS
4	AESR helps to impart a positive attitude toward agriculture.	3.10	1.01	3.31	0.85	0.77	Agreed	NS
5	AESR equips students with hands-on skills.	3.14	1.08	3.34	0.98	0.95	Agreed	NS
6	AESR help graduates to be self-reliance.	3.34	0.93	3.08	0.92	0.96	Agreed	NS
7	AESR help graduates to be self-employed.	3.06	0.92	3.34	0.90	0.91	Agreed	NS
8	AESR engaging in AESR activities could improve classroom learning.	3.41	0.87	3.15	0.85	0.56	Agreed	NS
9	Mental and hands-on activities are the prerequisite for developing inquiry mind.	3.16	0.84	3.26	0.89	0.96	Agreed	NS
10	Physical work makes the brain active.	3.49	0.92	3.52	0.93	0.68	Agreed	NS

Key: NS = Not Significant

Table 1 revealed that all the ten items had their mean values ranged from 3.06 to 3.52, which were above the benchmark of 2.50. Thus, it means that respondents agreed on the 10 items as important for the revitalization of agricultural education for self-reliance of students in colleges of education in the study area. The standard deviation of the responses of the respondents on the 10 items ranged from 0.68 to 1.08, indicating that respondents were not far in their opinions of responses from one another. The data on the hypothesis in Table 1 has shown that all the 10 items had the p-values ranged from 0.56 to 0.97, which were greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and NCE students on the importance of revitalization of agricultural education for self-reliance of students in the colleges of

education in Benue State, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between two groups was not rejected on the 10 items.

Research Question Two

What are the strategies to impart positive attitudes to students toward agricultural education for involvement in agriculture for self-reliance?

Research Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of NCE students and lecturers on the strategies of imparting positive attitudes into students toward agricultural education for involvement in agriculture for self-reliance.

The answer to this research question and the hypothesis testing are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test Analysis of the Responses of NCE Students and Lecturers on strategies to impart Positive Attitudes into students toward Agricultural Education for Involvement in Agriculture for Self-reliance in Colleges of Education (N=365)

S/N	Item Statement	\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	p-value	Remark	H ₀
1	NCE graduates have a negative attitude towards agriculture, despite it's the mainstay of the country's economy and offering an opportunity for employment.	3.37	0.67	3.37	0.68	0.89	Agreed	NS
2	Negative attitude by NCE graduates to agriculture has been justified by the increase by the rural-urban exodus.	3.36	0.68	3.56	0.66	0.90	Agreed	NS
3	Agricultural activities through AESR will help NCE graduates perceive agriculture positively as a source of livelihood.	3.33	1.02	3.32	1.05	0.91	Agreed	NS
4	The agricultural education curriculum needed to be revitalized to integrate agricultural activities for NCE graduates to perceive it as a potential sector for individual and community development.	3.06	1.06	3.13	1.05	0.97	Agreed	NS
5	Agricultural education for self-reliance activities if integrating into curriculum adequately it will enhance positive attitudes of students toward agriculture.	3.15	1.01	3.13	1.02	0.96	Agreed	NS

6	Agricultural education for self-reliance experience as a vehicle for learning allows the curriculum to be made relevant for learners.	3.60	0.68	3.62	0.66	0.77	Agreed	NS
7	Agricultural education for self-reliance activities helps identify potential skill in the learners for the area of mastery.	3.37	0.95	3.43	0.91	0.77	Agreed	NS
8	Prior experiences of agricultural education for self-reliance and possibly developing knowledge and positive attitudes of students.	3.11	0.75	3.54	0.67	0.87	Agreed	NS

Key: NS=Not Significant

Data presented in Table 2 revealed that all the 8 items had their mean values ranged from 3.06 to 3.62, which are above the benchmark of 2.50. This means that the respondents agreed that all the items are the methods to impart positive attitudes into students towards agricultural education in Benue State, Nigeria. The standard deviation of the respondents on the 8 items ranged from 0.66 to 1.12, indicating that responses of the respondents are not far-fetched from each other. Hypothesis 2 on the 8 items had the p-values ranging from 0.77 to 0.97, which are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance. It simply means there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and NCE students on the strategies of imparting positive attitudes into students towards agricultural education in colleges of education in the study area. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups was not rejected.

Research Question Three

What are the inadequate competencies of lecturers in imparting agricultural education learning activities into students for self-reliance?

Research Hypothesis Three

There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of NCE students and lecturers on the inadequate competencies of lecturers in imparting agricultural education learning activities for self-reliance.

The answer to this research question and the hypothesis testing are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test Analysis of the Responses of NCE Students and Lecturers on Inadequate Competencies of Lecturers in imparting Agricultural Education Activities for Self-reliance in Colleges of Education (N=365)

S/N	Item Statement	\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	p-value	Remark	H ₀
1	Lecturers are important stakeholders in the AESR activities.	3.37	0.82	3.41	0.81	0.75	Agreed	NS
2	Lecturers are not adequately equipped in utilizing AESR activities to enable learners' experiences to be focused during classroom learning.	3.16	1.04	3.14	1.03	0.90	Agreed	NS
3	The challenges of ASER policy implementation in Nigeria are that pedagogical potential is not understood.	3.44	0.63	3.47	0.64	0,75	Agreed	NS
4	Train and retraining of lecturers to utilize experiences, skills and knowledge to be developed via outdoor activities for classroom teaching.	3.14	0.94	3.38	1.02	0.78	Agreed	NS
5	The present curriculum for AESR activities is inadequate to equip lecturers with skills and knowledge to utilize for outdoor activities for learning.	3.17	0.79	3.23	0.77	0.07	Agreed	NS
6	Training of Lecturers could be done through in-service training by stakeholders or education or government	3.45	1.06	3.41	0.78	0.54	Agreed	NS
7	AESR activities needed a revitalization in colleges of education by reviewing the curriculum.	3.40	0.78	3.46	0.78	0.54	Agreed	NS
8	The specific quota of budget allocation for ASER for in-service training of lecturers should be considered by stakeholders to fill the gap.	3.48	0.74	3.47	0.73	0.86	Agreed	NS

Key: Not Significant

Table 3 has shown that all the 8 items had their mean values ranged from 3.14 to 3.48, which are above the benchmark of 2.50. This means that the respondents agreed that all the

8 items are the competencies needed by the lecturers to adequately equip students for AESR activities in colleges of education in Benue state. The standard deviation of the respondents on the items ranged from 0.63 to 1.09 indicating that there was no significant variation in the responses of the respondents. The data on the hypothesis showed that p-values in Table 3 are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and NCE students on the inadequate competencies of lecturers in imparting AESR activities to students in colleges of education in Benue state. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between two groups was not rejected.

Discussion

The result in Table 1 showed that lecturers and students in the study area have agreed that all 10 items are the importance of revitalization of agricultural education for self-reliance of students in colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria, since the respondents agreed with all items. The result also indicated that there was no statistically significant difference between the mean ratings. Therefore, there is a need for revitalization of agricultural education for self-reliance of students in colleges of education. This agrees with Agbulu and Olaitan (2002) who indicated that AESR help imparts positive attitude toward agricultural education for self-reliance and improve classroom learning.

The findings in Table 2 showed that all are the methods to impart positive attitudes to students' towards agricultural education in the colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. Hence, the respondents agreed with all the mean values above the benchmark of 2.50. The result also revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of the responses of the two groups on the 8 items, which P-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. For that reason, the null hypotheses were not rejected for the items. This has shown that lecturers and students have agreed on positive attitudes towards AESR programme for graduates needed for self-reliance. This agrees with Ahmad, Krogh and Ghotterrud (2014) who earlier observed that for the young generation to achieve self-reliance, agricultural activities need to be part and parcel of the school learning. The authors further explained that this will be possible through the revitalization of AESR activities, which proved to enhance positive attitude toward agriculture. This also agrees with Kadenyi and Kariuki (2011) who found that the use of agricultural experience as a vehicle for learning, which allows the curriculum to be made relevant to learner's prior experience and possibly developing knowledge, positive attitude and skills identifiable as important nationwide.

Table 3 revealed that respondents agreed on the 8 items lecturers' inadequate competencies in imparting agricultural education self-reliance activities into students in colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. This means that lecturers and NCE students agreed that all the 8 items on inadequate competencies of lecturers imparting AESR activities into students in colleges of education are needed. The responses agreed with all the mean values are above the benchmark of 2.50. The results also showed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of the responses of the two groups on the 8 items, whose p-values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. For this reason, the null hypothesis was not rejected for the 8 items. This has shown that the respondents have agreed on the lecturer's inadequate competencies in imparting agricultural education for self-

reliance into students in colleges of education in Benue State, Nigeria. The findings have shown that although lecturers are important stakeholders in AESR activities, however, they not adequately trained in imparting the activities AESR into students to enable them to develop skills to focus on after classroom learning. This is in submission to Ahmad *et al.*, (2014) findings which claim that one of the main challenges of the AESR policy implementation in Nigeria, is that it's pedagogical potential is not understood and therefore, not utilized by lecturers. Lecturers are not trained to utilize experiences and knowledge developed through outdoor activities in classroom teaching.

Conclusion

This study has presented respondents views on the relevance of the AESR in contemporary education in colleges of education. Generally, respondents were of the view that AESR activities are helpfully imparting a positive attitude toward agriculture, improving classroom learning and developing good social behaviour/skills such as cooperation and hardworking, equipping students with hands-on skills that are very important in making them cope with everyday life demands. Lastly, it helps in developing positive attitudes, skills and knowledge which would help them employ themselves, be self-reliant and strengthen government and colleges of education linkages. Besides, the respondents agreed that the impediment of the revitalization of AESR in colleges of education also includes lecturers' inadequate knowledge and skills to utilize experiences developed by learners when participating in AESR activities, shortage of competent lecturers and inadequate resources for implementation of AESR curriculum at colleges on the importance of its activities.

Based, on these findings, it is concluded that responses of respondents agreed with revitalization of AESR in Nigeria. Most of the challenges facing the AESR revitalization process as per respondents' views are manageable if the linkages between the concerned authorities become strong. The strong tiers become the foundation for developing mutual interests, positive attitudes, trust and relationship among the parties involved. Therefore, appropriate strategies for re-introducing and integrating AESR activities should be considered while taking account of the findings of the study. The strategies include capacity building of lecturers through training and re-training on the importance of the concerned authorities, developing partnership programmes aiming at the pathway to contribute to students' self-reliance education policy. However, the revitalisation process should be participative and empowering in order for the nation to benefit from the AESR activities/programmes.

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